

types. In West Africa, half were genotypes 1 and 3. The others, which may be major traditional cultivars, comprised genotypes 7, 12, 11, 8. The latter group may belong to a member of hill rices in Southeast Asia (see figure).

North America, particularly Texas State, showed variations of isoenzyme genotypes between japonica and javan-

ica. Consequently their origin may not be India and South China.

South America, particularly Brazil, showed simple variation. Most cultivars belong to genotypes 12 and 11, corresponding to the typical javanicas. A similar variation is found only on Sumatra island in Asia. West Africa and the Americas have a particular type of este-

rase isoenzyme genotypes. These are not indica (Indian rices) or sinica (Chinese hsien), but are more closely related hill rices or javanicas found in Upper Burma, northern Thailand, Laos, Sumatra, and southern Yunnan Province of China. ✎

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Performance of IR42 and IR48 in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

Nguyen van Luat, Bui Ba Bong, Nguyen Minh Chau, and J. Chandra Mohan, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (IRRI), O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam

IRRI early and intermediate maturity varieties and breeding lines have revolutionized rice cultivation in Vietnam. Two rice crops each year are now grown where one low-yielding, late-maturing local variety once grew. More than a dozen IRRI lines have been named and released for large-scale cultivation.

More than 65% of the rice area in Cuu Long Delta (Vietnamese portion of Mekong Delta) is planted to IRRI varie-

ties. Some popular varieties in large-scale cultivation are: NN3A (IR36), NN6A (IR2307-247-2-2-3), NN7A (IR9129-192-2-3-5), NN8A (IR2070-199-3-6-6), and NN2B (IR2823-399-5-6). Average yields are 3.5-4.0 t/ha.

NN4B (IR42) and NN5B (IR48) were introduced in 1981. Their performance, particularly in adverse soils, is encouraging (Table 1). Both varieties have intermediate maturity (130-145 days), tolerance for soil stresses, semitall plant height (100-120 cm), and resist lodging. NN4B yields higher on saline soils than the popular local variety Than Nong Do. NN5B yields more than local varieties Tieu Mo and Bay Danh on acid sulfate soils. Both varieties have yielded

more than an earlier IRRI line, NN2B, on alluvial soils. In seed multiplication plots at 10 sites, yields were 4-9 t/ha.

Both varieties resist brown planthopper, and NN5B resists rice blast (Table 2). Neither variety, however, resists sheath blight. Both varieties are popular with farmers because they are generally free of pest damage in normal field conditions.

Because NN4B and NN5B are popular, produce high yields, and are insect and disease resistant the Cuu Long RRI is making special efforts to rapidly multiply seeds on a large scale. ✎

Table 1. Yield level^a of NN4B and NN5B in early mua season (May-Oct), Cuu Long, Delta, Vietnam.

Variety	Hau Giang Province (alluvial soil)			Long An Province (acid sulfate soil), rainfed wetland		Minh Hai Province (saline soil), rainfed lowland,	Average yield (t/ha)
	Irrigated, 1980	Rainfed 1979 1981		1980	1981	1980	
NN4B (IR42)	6.63 a	3.38 a	3.13 b	2.91 b	3.00 b	3.96 a	3.84
NN5B (IR48)	6.45 a	3.45 a	4.18 a	3.53 a	4.20 a	3.54 b	4.22
Check ^b	4.20 b	2.85 b	3.13 b	2.60 b	2.90 b	3.15 c	3.18

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5%. ^bVariety check: alluvial: NN2B; acid sulfate: Tieu Mo (1980), Bay Danh (1981); saline: Than Nong Do.

Table 2. Reaction of NN4B and NN5B to rice pest in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.^a

Variety	Brown planthopper		Leaf blast		Bacterial leaf blight		Sheath blight	
	Infested (%)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Disease index (%)	Reaction
NN4B (IR42)	14	R	4-7	MS-S	3	MR	90	HS
NN5B (IR48)	30	MR	1	R	5	MS	80	S
Resistant check ^b	26	MR	1	R	1	R	100	HS
Susceptible check ^b	100	HS	4-9	MS-HS	8	S	100	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bResistant check for BPH: IR36, LB: Tetep, BLB: Cempo Selak, ShB: IET4699. Susceptible check for BPH: TN1, LB: NN7a BLB: IR8, ShB: IR36.